

Influence of the Polymer Matrix on the Mechanical Response of a Unidirectional Composite

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ABSTRACT

A finite element micromechanics analysis is used to predict the influence of the matrix on the unidirectional lamina properties of a composite laminate. Experimentally determined epoxy matrix properties are used as a basis for comparison for the many new polymer matrix systems currently being developed. The influence of increased strain to failure of the matrix on bulk properties such as coefficients of thermal and moisture expansion are presented. In addition, local stress distributions in the matrix around individual fibers are shown.

INTRODUCTION

The composites community is witnessing a rapid development of new and improved polymers for use as matrix materials in high performance composites at the present time, after a decade of relative inactivity. In addition to greatly improved high temperature polyimides, a large family of bismalimides is being introduced, along with higher strain to failure epoxy systems.

The development of composite materials during the past several decades has emphasized the improvement of fiber and interface properties. However, the polymer chemist is now beginning to ask, "How can the matrix be modified to further improve the performance of the composite?" Since the polymer matrix typically exhibits at least some degree of nonlinear response prior to failure, and is subject to a very complex stress state induced by the fibers present in the composite, determination of the contribution of the matrix is a complex process.

Concurrently, theoretical methods of predicting the response of a composite have been considerably refined during the past few years. In particular, the so-called micromechanics analyses, which predict the composite response of a unidirectional ply as well as the local stress states in fiber and matrix, are applicable. One such micromechanics analysis, developed by the author and his colleagues and well documented in the literature (1-3), has been used to predict the influences of variations of the polymer matrix properties on composite response to various combinations of temperature and moisture.

Basic experimental data are available for the epoxy matrix materials in

current use, including complete stress-strain curves to failure for various test temperatures and moisture contents (3). In the present study, the influence of specific variations of this matrix behavior have been modeled, to help identify those modifications of the polymer which, if achieved, would improve the performance of the resulting composite. Variations which have been considered include matrix modulus, strain to failure, ultimate strength, thermal and moisture expansion, and the temperature- and moisture-dependence of these matrix properties.

CONSTITUENT MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Epoxy matrix materials in common use at the present time are represented by the Hercules 3501-6 resin system (3) of Figure 1. These data were generated in the author's laboratory using dog-boned flat tensile specimens. The results are presented in the form of octahedral shear stress-octahedral shear strain curves for use in the micromechanics analysis. Data are presented for two temperatures, $T = 21^\circ\text{C}$ and $T = 150^\circ\text{C}$; M is the moisture content, in weight percent. A corresponding set of hypothetical resin matrix curves are presented in Figure 2. These curves are based upon preliminary results obtained by McLean (4), but are representative of the high strain to failure resins currently being developed. For reference, the corresponding tensile strains to failure at the room temperature, dry condition are 1.9 percent for the Hercules 3501-6 epoxy, and 9.0 percent for

Fig. 1. Typical Octahedral Shear Stress-Octahedral Shear Strain Curves for Hercules 3501-6 Epoxy Matrix

Fig. 2. Typical Octahedral Shear Stress-Octahedral Shear Strain Curves for a High Strength, Ductile Epoxy

the ductile epoxy. The room temperature, dry Young's modulus values are 4.3 GPa and 2.6 GPa, respectively. That is, there is a distinct trade-off between strain to failure and initial stiffness. For lack of specific data, the Poisson's ratio (0.34), coefficient of thermal expansion ($40 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$), and coefficient of moisture expansion ($2 \times 10^{-3}/\%M$) of the Hercules resin at room temperature, dry conditions (3) were assumed for both matrix materials.

The properties of the fiber are also required as input to the analysis. Three different fibers will be studied in combination with the two matrix materials, viz, a high modulus graphite (Celanese GY-70), a low modulus graphite (Hercules AS), and S glass. The required material properties are shown in Table 1, these literature values being taken from a summary presented in Reference (5). Over the temperature range of interest, i.e., between room temperature and the cure temperature of the resulting composites (177°C), these fiber properties are assumed to be essentially constant. Correspondingly, they are assumed to be independent of moisture.

Table 1
Fiber Properties

Fiber Type	Axial Strength σ_{ℓ}^u , MPa	Axial Modulus E_{ℓ} , GPa	Transverse Modulus E_t , GPa	Major Poisson's Ratio $\nu_{\ell t}$	In-Plane Poisson's Ratio ν_{tt}	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion $10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$	
						Axial α_{ℓ}	Transverse α_t
GY-70 Graphite	1720	520	6.9	0.20	0.25	-1.10	18
AS Graphite	3100	220	13.8	0.20	0.25	-0.36	18
S Glass	4830	86	86	0.22	0.22	5	5

ANALYTICAL MODEL

Complete details of the micromechanics model utilized in the present study have been presented elsewhere (1-3). In summary, an elastoplastic, generalized plane strain analysis has been formulated, incorporating an octahedral shear stress yield criterion, the Prandtl-Reuss flow rule, temperature- and moisture-dependent matrix material properties, and anisotropic (transversely isotropic) fibers. A finite element solution incorporating constant strain triangular elements is used.

For purposes of the present study, all composites were assumed to have a 60 percent fiber volume, with the circular cross section fibers arranged in a square packing array. Because of the double axes of symmetry associated with this regular fiber packing, it is only necessary to model one quadrant of the repeating element, which consists of a single fiber surrounded by a square cross section of matrix material. In the present study, this one quadrant has been modeled using 230 finite elements and 135 node points.

PREDICTED INTERNAL STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS

The composites are assumed to be cured at 177°C, cooled to room temperature, and then allowed to absorb moisture. While the stress distributions in the fibers are predicted as well as the matrix stresses (6), only the latter will be presented here, along with fiber-matrix interface normal and shear stress distributions. All matrix stress components are predicted by the analysis, including the three principal stresses, the octahedral shear stress, and the maximum shear stress. However, for brevity, only selected stress distributions will be presented here.

Results will be presented for S glass fibers and GY-70 graphite fibers, the AS graphite fiber of Table 1 representing an intermediate case between these two extremes.

S Glass/Epoxy

The maximum principal stresses, the minimum principal stresses, and the octahedral shear stresses are shown in Figures 3, 4, and 5, respectively. These are the predicted stress states due only to cooldown from the 177°C cure temperature to room temperature, i.e., these are the curing residual stresses. In each figure, the results for the conventional epoxy matrix (Hercules 3501-6) are shown first, and then the results for the ductile epoxy.

As can be seen by comparing Figures 3a and 3b, the maximum principal stresses in the higher modulus conventional epoxy are almost twice as high as

a) Conventional Epoxy

b) Ductile Epoxy

Fig. 3. Maximum Principal Stresses (MPa) in an S Glass/Epoxy Composite after Cooldown from the 177°C Cure Temperature to Room Temperature.

those in the ductile epoxy. While the most negative minimum principal stresses shown in Figure 4a for the conventional epoxy matrix are essentially equal to those in the ductile epoxy matrix (Figure 4b), viz, about -20 MPa, the most positive minimum principal stresses are much higher in the conventional epoxy.

a) Conventional Epoxy

b) Ductile Epoxy

Fig. 4. Minimum Principal Stresses (MPa) in an S Glass/Epoxy Composite after Cooldown from the 177°C Cure Temperature to Room Temperature

Octahedral shear stress plots are very useful in studying the influence of the interaction of the several stress components acting at a point simultaneously. In Figure 5, the calculated octahedral shear stresses have been normalized by dividing by the yield value at the room temperature, dry condition. The normalizing value of 37.2 MPa used for both matrix systems is the actual measured value for the Hercules 3501-6 epoxy. Thus, both plots are normalized in the same manner and can be compared directly. As can be seen, the octahedral shear stress in the conventional epoxy is 50 percent higher than that in the ductile epoxy.

a) Conventional Epoxy

b) Ductile Epoxy

Fig. 5. Octahedral Shear Stresses (Normalized by Dividing by the Matrix Room Temperature, Dry Yield Stress of 37.2 MPa) in an S Glass/Epoxy Composite after Cooldown from the 177°C Cure Temperature to Room Temperature.

Fiber-matrix interface debonding is a common failure mode in composites. These stresses can also be readily predicted, as indicated in Figures 6 and 7. In Figure 6, the normal stresses around the fiber-matrix interface are shown. The arrows pointing outward indicate tensile normal stresses; the arrows pointing inward indicate compressive normal stresses. As will be noted, the highest interface normal stresses are more than 50 percent higher in the conventional epoxy matrix, but are compressive. Thus, if both composites were to be subsequently subjected to a transverse tensile loading, the higher compressive curing residual stress would in fact be more favorable. As indicated in Figure 7, the shear stress at the interface is also higher for the conventional matrix composite. Here the arrows pointing outward indicate a positive shear stress, while the arrows pointing inward indicate a negative shear stress. It will be noted that the highest shear stresses do not occur at the same locations around the interface as the normal stresses.

a) Conventional Epoxy

b) Ductile Epoxy

Fig. 6. Fiber-Matrix Interface Normal Stresses (MPa) in an S Glass/Epoxy Composite after Cooldown from the 177°C Cure Temperature to Room Temperature.

Fig. 7. Fiber-Matrix Interface Shear Stresses (MPa) in an S Glass/Epoxy Composite after Cooldown from the 177°C Cure Temperature to Room Temperature.

Often a composite is to be used in a humid environment. Most polymer matrices will absorb a considerable amount of moisture, many on the order of five to seven percent, as shown in Figures 1 and 2. Since the coefficient of moisture expansion is high relative to the coefficient of thermal expansion (as previously stated, representative values of $2 \times 10^{-3}/\%M$ and $40 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}C$, respectively, as determined experimentally (7), have been assumed in the present study), moisture-induced stresses can be even more significant than thermal stresses. For example, the influence of absorbing only 0.8 weight percent moisture into the S glass/epoxy composite (which is equivalent to a 3 weight percent moisture absorption in the matrix itself, the S glass fibers absorbing no moisture) is shown in Figure 8. This corresponds to approximately a 50 percent relative humidity environment for a sufficient time to reach equilibrium. By comparing Figure 6 with Figure 8, it can be seen that the curing residual (thermal) stresses have been negated by the 0.8 weight percent composite moisture absorption. In fact, the stresses have

Fig. 8. Fiber-Matrix Interface Normal Stresses (MPa) in an S Glass/Epoxy Composite after 0.8 Weight Percent Moisture Absorption

actually reversed sign. That is, for a slightly lower moisture absorption, the interface stresses would have been very nearly zero. The subsequent moisture-induced swelling of the matrix offsets the effects of the thermal contraction induced during cooldown. The interface shear stress results were similar.

As the moisture content is subsequently increased, the stresses continue to increase. The magnitudes of the interface normal stresses are indicated in Figure 9 for a composite weight gain of 1.4 percent for the conventional epoxy, and 1.7 percent for the ductile epoxy (corresponding to 5 percent and 6 percent, respectively, in the matrix itself). As can be seen, the tensile normal stresses are about 50 percent higher than the compressive stresses previously induced by the cooldown stresses alone (Figure 6). The interface shear stresses are not shown here as they indicate similar trends. As indicated in Figure 9a, the interface stresses in the conventional epoxy matrix composite are somewhat higher than those in the ductile matrix composite (Figure 9b), even though the moisture content is less. In fact, the conventional epoxy matrix composite is predicted to fail (microcrack) at the interface at an absorbed moisture content of slightly less than 1.5 weight percent. The much higher strain to failure of the ductile matrix permits it to absorb these high local strains without failure. This is an obvious advantage of a more ductile matrix.

Fig. 9. Fiber-Matrix Interface Normal Stresses (MPa) in an S Glass/Epoxy Composite after a Specified Amount of Moisture Absorption.

GY-70 Graphite/Epoxy

As noted in Table 1, the GY-70 graphite fiber has a very high axial modulus, and is also highly anisotropic, whereas the S glass fiber is isotropic, with a modulus only about one-sixth as high as that of the GY-70 graphite. The transverse modulus of the GY-70 graphite fiber is much lower than the modulus of the S glass fiber, however, actually about 12 times less. Thus, the mismatch of moduli of the fiber and matrix in the transverse direction is much less for the GY-70 graphite/epoxy composites than for the S-glass/epoxy composites. This should result in lower matrix and interface stresses in the graphite/epoxy

composite, which the micromechanics analysis demonstrates. The stress state is complicated considerably by the high degree of thermal anisotropy of the graphite fiber, however, and the fact that the axial thermal expansion of the graphite fiber is actually negative (see Table 1). That is, during cooldown from the cure temperature, the graphite fiber actually expands while the surrounding matrix is attempting to contract. This induces high axial tensile stresses in the matrix, and influences the stresses in the transverse plane via Poisson effects. Examples of resulting stress states in the GY-70 graphite/epoxy due to cooldown only are shown in Figures 10 and 11.

Comparing Figures 3 and 10, it can be seen that the higher modulus and fiber anisotropy of the GY-70 graphite has a significant effect. For either matrix material, the stresses near the interface at 45° to the horizontal axis are much higher for the S glass fiber, even though the stresses in the regions of closest fiber spacing are about equal. On the other hand, the minimum principal stress distributions were similar, even though the magnitudes were more than 2.5 times higher for the S glass/epoxy composites. This clearly indicates that the higher modulus, anisotropic graphite fibers do not necessarily lead to more severe thermal residual stresses.

On the other hand, the lower modulus and more ductile matrix material is again an advantage for the graphite/epoxy composite, just as it was for the glass/epoxy system. Interestingly, the maximum principal stresses are only

Fig. 10. Maximum Principal Stresses (MPa) in a GY-70 Graphite/Epoxy Composite after Cooldown from the 177°C Cure Temperature to Room Temperature.

about one-half as high (see Figure 10), while the minimum principal stresses were not significantly different. All of this seemingly unusual response can be fully explained, of course, by the micromechanics analysis.

Fiber-matrix interface normal stresses due to cooldown of the GY-70 graphite/epoxy composites are shown in Figure 11. A comparison with the results for the S glass/epoxy composites (Figure 6) indicates these normal stresses to be about 2.5 times less also, consistent with the principal stresses. The interface shear stresses, not shown here, exhibited similar trends.

The influence of adding moisture to the GY-70 graphite/epoxy composites is indicated in Figure 12. The 1.9 weight percent moisture in the composites corresponds to 6 weight percent in the epoxy matrix. That is, the same amount of moisture has been added to these matrix materials as for the S glass/ductile epoxy composite of Figure 9b. The lower density of the graphite fiber relative

a) Conventional Epoxy

b) Ductile Epoxy

Fig. 11. Fiber-Matrix Interface Normal Stresses (MPa) in a GY-70 Graphite/Epoxy Composite after Cooldown from the 177°C Cure Temperature to Room Temperature.

a) Conventional Epoxy

b) Ductile Epoxy

Fig. 12. Maximum Principal Stresses (MPa) in a GY-70 Graphite/Epoxy Composite after 1.9 Weight Percent Moisture Absorption.

to glass explains the higher moisture weight gain of the graphite/epoxy composite, i.e., 1.9 weight percent versus 1.6 weight percent. As can be seen by comparing the results in Figure 12, the stresses in the conventional epoxy matrix composite are higher than in the ductile epoxy matrix composite.

COMPOSITE EXPANSION COEFFICIENTS

In addition to the internal stress distributions, which define yielding and eventual crack initiation, the micromechanics analysis is capable of predicting many other properties of the composite. For example, predictions of stiffness

properties, along with experimental correlations, are presented in Reference (8). Predicted coefficients of thermal expansion and moisture expansion are also of particular interest, some results having been presented in Reference (7) for conventional matrix materials.

Table 2 indicates the influence of the ductile epoxy matrix on the predicted room temperature thermal expansion coefficients, for all three types of fibers. As can be seen, some of the differences between the Hercules 3501-6 epoxy and the ductile epoxy are quite large. Such differences can be particularly important when designing thermally stable structures.

Room temperature moisture expansion coefficients are presented in Table 3. Again, the differences are significant, particularly when dimensionally stable structures are being designed.

Table 2
ROOM TEMPERATURE THERMAL EXPANSION COEFFICIENTS
OF VARIOUS UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES

FIBER TYPE	COEFFICIENTS OF THERMAL EXPANSION, $10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$			
	HERCULES 3501-6 EPOXY		HIGH STRENGTH, DUCTILE EPOXY	
	AXIAL	TRANSVERSE	AXIAL	TRANSVERSE
S Glass	6.28	19.9	5.79	19.9
AS Graphite	0.201	31.0	-0.012	30.4
GY-70 Graphite	-0.864	32.2	-0.950	31.5

Table 3
ROOM TEMPERATURE MOISTURE EXPANSION COEFFICIENTS
OF VARIOUS UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES

FIBER TYPE	COEFFICIENTS OF MOISTURE EXPANSION, $10^{-3}/\%M$			
	HERCULES 3501-6 EPOXY		HIGH STRENGTH, DUCTILE EPOXY	
	AXIAL	TRANSVERSE	AXIAL	TRANSVERSE
S Glass	0.257	2.99	0.136	2.65
AS Graphite	0.091	3.04	0.054	2.90
GY-70 Graphite	0.038	3.36	0.023	3.12

CONCLUSION

The various results presented here clearly indicate the importance of matrix properties on the composite response. The micromechanics analysis serves as an excellent tool in studying the complex interactions between fiber and matrix. As the many new polymer matrix systems currently being developed are characterized, it is expected that such an analysis will become extremely valuable as a screening tool.

Even the limited results presented here demonstrate that there is always a trade-off when constituent properties are altered. Only by modeling the many parameters involved using a rigorous analysis can thoughtful decisions be made. To fabricate and test each new candidate composite system is prohibitive, in terms of both cost and time.

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